

A NOTE ON THE REACTIONS AND EXCHANGE OF ACTIVE IODINE IN INORGANIC SYSTEM.

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Experiments with natural radio-elements have established complete exchange of activity between atoms existing in the same valence type in the compounds and no exchange between atoms in the ionic and co-valent state. But with artificially produced active elements quite different results have been reported. Exchange of active iodine between sodium iodide and methyl iodide, or iodoform in alcohol or acetone has been observed by McKay (*Nature*, 1937, **139**, 283), it being immaterial which component of the system was active originally. Similar results have been obtained by other workers as well (Juliusburger, Topley and Weiss, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, **3**, 437; Hull, Shiflett and Lind, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 535, 1822). In the pure inorganic system it has, however, been found in the case of co-ordination compounds that no exchange occurs between the co-ordinatively bound chlorine within the complex zone and the ionic chlorine outside (Ettle and Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1939, 1490). It was, therefore, considered interesting to examine such exchange reactions between co-valently and co-ordinatively bound atoms within one and the same complex zone, in other words, to explore any possible difference between the primary and auxiliary valencies of a central atom. Artificially produced radio-elements can alone serve as indicators for this purpose.

With radioactive iodine as an indicator we have examined qualitatively the exchange reactions between mercuric iodide and ammonium iodide; the iodine of the latter compound was rendered active by previous irradiation of its solution with slow neutrons. The resulting complex $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HgI}_4$ was subsequently decomposed into its components by dilution with a large quantity of water. The precipitated mercuric iodide was found to be active when examined in a Geiger-Müller counter. Similar results were obtained with bismuth and lead iodide which form complex $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BiI}_4$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PbI}_4$ respectively.

where Me = Hg, Bi, or Pb; I* represents active iodine atom.

Similar results have also been reported by Polesitzki (*Compt. rend.*

Acad. Sci. U.R.S.S., 1939 **34**, 540), in the case of KI and HgI₂; the complex K₂HgI₄ was decomposed by silver nitrate into AgI and HgI₂.

The results show that there is no essential difference between the normal co-valency and the co-ordinate co-valency.

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